

1

*Consumption
Patterns on
Mainstream SVoD
Services Platforms
Across 10 European
Countries*

IOANNA ARCHONTAKI

PHD CANDIDATE AND RESEARCHER
DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNICATION AND MEDIA STUDIES OF THE
NATIONAL AND KAPODISTRIAN UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS
IOANNARX@MEDIA.UOA.GR
[HTTPS://ORCID.ORG/0000-0001-6712-0531](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6712-0531)

ACHILLEAS KARADIMITRIOU

ADJUNCT LECTURER AND RESEARCHER
DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNICATION AND MEDIA STUDIES OF THE
NATIONAL AND KAPODISTRIAN UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS
AKARADIM@MEDIA.UOA.GR
[HTTPS://ORCID.ORG/0000-0003-3670-968X](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-3670-968X)

ILIANA GIANNOULI

ADJUNCT LECTURER AND RESEARCHER
DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNICATION AND MEDIA STUDIES OF THE
NATIONAL AND KAPODISTRIAN UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS
GIANNOUL@MEDIA.UOA.GR
[HTTPS://ORCID.ORG/0009-0000-2634-351X](https://orcid.org/0009-0000-2634-351X)

STYLIANOS PAPATHANASSOPOULOS

PROFESSOR OF MEDIA POLICY AND ORGANIZATION
DEPARTMENT OF COMMUNICATION AND MEDIA STUDIES - NATIONAL AND
KAPODISTRIAN UNIVERSITY OF ATHENS
SPAPATH@MEDIA.UOA.GR
[HTTPS://ORCID.ORG/0000-0001-7946-6310](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7946-6310)

ABSTRACT

Over the last years, media viewing behaviors have undergone remarkable changes resulting from the wide availability of streaming services and VoD platforms. Competition between European and American content has left the former in a dire situation, while the efforts from the EU to regulate the new audiovisual field have proved mostly inefficient. In this paper, we aim to assess the current availability and diversity of Video On Demand content in ten European countries by analyzing Netflix catalogues based on a set of variables (size, year of production, ratings, and genres). By studying the consumption patterns of European audio-visual works on various SVoD services platforms we try to evaluate the penetration of European audiovisual products in the global market, juxtaposing the results with the increasing investment in European productions. Finally, by comparing the consumption of the most popular genres in ten European countries over the period 2020-2022, we review the algorithmic recommendations and content curation effects on the prominence of the European works and their consumption. The analysis enables us to further evaluate the success of EU's Audiovisual Media Services Directive call on content quotas addressed to VoD platforms and make further suggestions.

KEYWORDS: Video on demand, VoD consumption, SVoD platforms, Netflix, Europeanisation, audiovisual media, AVMSD, algorithmic recommendations.

INTRODUCTION

The Video-on-Demand (VoD) market in the European Union (EU) consists of powerful US-based companies offering Subscription Video-on-Demand (SVoD) services (Netflix, Amazon Prime Video, Apple TV+) along with less influential European companies like Viaplay (Denmark), Mubi (UK), BritBox (UK; as a joint effort of the BBC and ITV), Salto (France) and Videoland (The Netherlands). In such a competitive field, the major US conglomerates have staked their claim since US global streamers own over one third of SVoD (38%) and Transactional Video-on-Demand (TVoD) services (34%) in Europe. The programming content of SVoD services within the European territory is primarily composed of film and TV fiction (47%) and gradually embraces more diverse components through the presence, for example, of children and reality TV. In TVoD services, film and TV fiction content occupies a larger portion of the overall programming output (68%) at the expense of other genres, reflecting the big streaming services control of the market. A notable portion of on-demand services in Europe (21%) addresses non-domestic markets with three European countries (Ireland, the UK, and the Netherlands) operating as the greatest hubs for the major US global streaming players (Schneeberger, 2023).

The coexistence of national and international players takes place on unequal terms. Especially in the case of smaller media markets, it influences traditional broadcasters' budgets and thus affects their exploitation opportunities for investments in the international market, impeding, at the same time, their potential to make profitable Europe-oriented audiovisual content within the VoD services field. On the other hand, a handful of big global media companies, having achieved increased annual revenues, expand content investments in streaming services, establishing a new era of "peak TV". These developments have created an environment of uncertainty, framed by several challenges to produce European content (Komorowski et al., 2021).

The global reach of the most successful streamers has refueled the discussions of transnational media flows and power exertion since global streamers' tactics have altered the dynamics of transnational television trade. This means that TV distributors (both traditional TV channels and OTT operators), at least in Europe, are in a constant search for new formats of genres, which in turn has led to a continuous evolution, if not amalgamation, of traditional TV genres, such as infotainment, edutainment, docushows, reality and reality quiz shows. Moreover, the cost of the content rights has increased, especially due to the aggressive competition policy of over-the-top (OTT) operators in certain programming content (i.e., films). As exemplified by Netflix, which has proved the most aggressive of the global streaming platforms (Aguiar & Waldfoegel, 2018), the hoarding of film rights has even forced major Holly-

wood studios into looking for original online content in search of the proper business model (Pardo, 2012).

In this race for content, the problem of Europe lies in that it has great difficulty in competing with the American output, given that US-content proves dominant in SVoD services. Considering that the growth of VoD services platforms has led to more widely distributed consumption patterns among highly fragmented audience categories, a crucial question being raised is whether and to what extent the consumption of EU audiovisual works is being swallowed up by US audiovisual offerings.

Based on EUMEPLAT project findings (2020) (<https://www.eumeplat.eu/>), the present study utilizes secondary data to analyze the content available in the European Netflix libraries and compares it to the international ones. By examining and contrasting the contents of libraries worldwide, it becomes apparent that consumption patterns are shaped not solely by audience preferences, but also by the availability of audiovisual works to each specific audience. Additionally, the study examines the global performance of European audiovisual content across six different VoD platforms (Netflix, HBO, Amazon Prime, Disney+, iTunes, Google TV) to explore how audience's preferences for non-linear audiovisual content are influenced by the origin of audiovisual works. Finally, the study analyses genre-specific data for nine European Union (EU) countries (Bulgaria, Belgium, Czech Republic, Germany, Greece, Italy, Portugal, Spain, Sweden) and Turkey, over the period 2020-2022. The study focuses on two platforms, Netflix and HBO Max, in order to assess to what extent consumption patterns diversify within Europe. Through this comparison, we also highlight the effects of algorithmic recommendations and content curation processes on the prominence of European audiovisual works and their consumption.

TRANSNATIONAL TELEVISION: FROM TRADITIONAL SCHEDULING TO ALGORITHMIC FILTERING OF CONTENT

The global audiovisual industry is currently going through a “streaming war», or in more precise terms, finds itself in a state of new “competition dynamics” (Lobato & Lotz, 2018). This new competitive condition is dictated by a volatile communication field, where the logic of audiovisual content distribution and consumption has radically changed. Algorithmically curated catalogues of content affect users' selections, establishing a new way of watching audiovisual content that has totally departed from the flow of linear broadcasting. It is what Lobato (2018) describes as a new form of television acquiring a database character. The transition of the television world from scheduling to curation, as exemplified by the non-linear television services,

reflects a structural transformation of the audiovisual field characterized by the personalized offerings of content (Lotz, 2017).

The algorithmic filtering techniques and personalized recommendations methods invite targeted online users to discover film and television content. This practice, dubbed the discoverability issue, raises new challenges for policymakers (Lobato & Scarlata, 2022). Through this artificial discoverability, the user's attention is fully guided against a framework of more visible options at the expense of less visible ones. This amounts to interference with the user's private consumption process (Lobato & Scarlata, 2022). Therefore, the policy question being raised is whether SVoD services should be regulated in such a way as to place them under the same obligations (i.e., prominence rules) that were in force for public service broadcasters and pay-TV channels.

Various countries (Canada, Australia, the United Kingdom, and EU member-states) are currently engaged in regulatory discussions about the visibility and distinct identification of national productions in the realm of internet-distributed television, and particularly in SVoD services' expanding context. The policy rationale is not identical among the various media markets. Nevertheless, a common requirement is the necessity for "regulatory flexibility" to establish suitable measures that can effectively address specific discoverability issues within the framework of existing legislation.

In the UK, the emphasis is placed on the discoverability of PSBs in relation to SVoD, whereas in the EU the Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD) points to the need for visibility of the regional European content by a variety of methods discussed below. On the other hand, in Canada and Australia special attention is paid to the visibility of local content in SVoD interfaces through the introduction of relevant discoverability rules (Lobato & Scarlata, 2022). The combination of existing and emergent methodologies is proposed as a means for analyzing programming across several SVoD platforms (Lobato, 2018).

POWERFUL TRANSNATIONALISATION TRENDS IN THE AUDIOVISUAL FIELD

During the last decades technology and globalization have been considered the major factors in transforming the audiovisual industry. The advent of the 21st century was accompanied by the internationalisation of the TV content chain through the emergence of transnational TV networks and transnational programming formats with the latter becoming a multi-billion-dollar trading system under several business models such as big format owners undertaking productions in several territories worldwide (Chalaby, 2015, pp. 461-464). This global shift of the TV industry, permitting an increase in cross-border media

flows, was favoured by a new type of content value chain characterized by the coordination of TV content production on a global scale (Chalaby, 2016).

However, after the advent of streaming platforms which expanded rapidly into the global markets by adopting a model of investments in original content, being at the intersection between local and global, the audiovisual industry saw a great shift in production patterns and in transnational collaborations. A distinctive case is Netflix platform seeking international expansion by relying on a process of content localization through investments in Netflix original content drawing on local users' tastes and big data analytics (Iordache et al., 2022, p. 240).

In the platform era, informed by the internet or streaming television services, the appeal of foreign programming, mainly derived from the US market, has been perceived as "an unbalanced flow" against a background of a new wave of media imperialism. This is exemplified in Latin America's media field for which it is argued that the innovative nature of the new streaming flows of international audiovisual content, based on the feature of transversality, cuts across the traditional flows with the aid of direct targeting of online users made feasible by the algorithms and big data mechanisms. Transversality refers to the new trend of audiovisual content's dissemination across national and regional television flows, in line with online users' preferences and regardless of limitations imposed by geography, language or culture. This takes place in a context of "platform imperialism" where the diversely originated content provided by the media companies addresses national, regional and global audiences, however control and financial gains rest in the hands of US-based companies (Straubhaar, 2021, pp. 193-194).

These companies have set global aims by investing considerably in the international expansion of the audiovisual services and by adopting transnational market penetration strategies. From this perspective, Netflix has been described as a "disruptive agent" in the targeted markets (such as in the Ibero-American audiovisual field) since its agreements with local media companies or its initiatives aimed at exclusive content ("Netflix Originals") are believed to have provoked disorders at the political-regulatory and business level (Leiva et al., 2021, pp. 2-3).

Based on the rationale that the rise of platforms incorporates both continuities and discontinuities Chalaby (2023, pp. 14-15) evaluates the impact of streaming platforms on the TV industry by highlighting that they reflect the entrance of television to the digital/platform economy where the predominance of some firms is dependent on their great potential, financially and infrastructurally, to evolve at a globalized scale resulting in concentration of wealth and power. The process of digitalization and platformisation, under-

gone by the media and entertainment sectors, is argued to entail the adoption of an innovative business model relying on video content's monetization through subscription, advertising or pay-per-view patterns of audiovisual content consumption (Chalaby, 2023, pp. 3-7). The transition of television from broadcasting to streaming heralded the expansion of TV industry's structure with tech giants entering the field having as assets their large scale, a strong investment potential and an appropriate infrastructure for the streaming sector, employable across multiple services and platforms (Chalaby, 2023, p. 13).

Entering transnational collaborations through investments in European productions powerful SVoD platforms such as Netflix enabled the exposure of wider audiences to non-national European works while, at the same time, the video-on-demand providers have managed to enter European markets based on a wider transnational content. Moreover, by adopting an expansion strategy for their international presence the audiovisual sector has been led to a redefinition of successful-popular television based on global terms. The discourses of streaming success articulated by Netflix executives and creative personnel point to the formulation of Netflix's audience as global and undifferentiated (Wayne et al., 2023).

In this new platform-dominated ecosystem "an asymmetrical relationship of interdependence between the West, primarily the U.S., and many developing powers" has emerged, which is described as "platform imperialism" (Jin, 2013, p. 154). The current developments in the platform market suggest a technological lead of U.S. based companies, enabling them to exert their influence on other countries, since technology is argued not to be value neutral and platforms are often perceived as embodying the beliefs of its developers, occasionally conflicting with the values of their prospective consumers (Ibid.).

Overall, the evolution of transnational internet distributed video services has shifted the dynamics of broadcast and cable/satellite services and has disrupted the national audiovisual markets. In effect, these services, characterised by different technological affordances, such as enabling online users to have on-demand access to library content, represent a new distribution technology requiring a process of policy tools reconsideration (Lotz, 2019) within an updated regulatory paradigm.

THE REGULATORY CHALLENGES BEHIND THE EMERGENCE OF GLOBAL STREAMING PLATFORMS

According to the European Audiovisual Observatory, among all audiovisual works found in VoD catalogues, European works (films and TV series) are represented by 32% (EU27 audiovisual works are represented by 21%, while

other European works by 11%) as opposed to US productions having accomplished the highest representation rate (49%). Moreover, the findings reveal that among all EU27 works hosted in SVoD catalogues, the majority (79%) was of non-national origin (Grece, 2022).

The predominance of US content availability, which affects consumption patterns, is also reflected in a report issued by the European Commission (2023). Regarding VoD platforms, the report's data reveal that actual consumption is dominated by US works, accounting for 59% of the viewing time, whereas they only account for 47% of all the works available. EU works constituted 28% of all works available in the VoD catalogues under the sample, but their consumption amounted to only 22% of the viewing time – and was found to be concentrated on a fewer number of titles than US works. Non-national EU works account for half of EU works available and up to 9% of the viewing time.

The regulation of audiovisual content provided by transnational digital platforms through their SVoD catalogues is currently a debatable issue raising concerns for its efficacy among scholars and policymakers. The European Union (EU) has also experienced a fluctuation between liberalization and interventionism in its audiovisual policies. While EU policy has largely been reactive to technological advancements, this ongoing debate has led to the formation of two entrenched factions within the Union. Over time, the European Union has shown a further shift towards the interventionist approach by extending quotas implementation on VoD platforms. This change in policy was driven by European policymakers recognizing the significant shifts in viewing habits due to the dominance of streaming media and VoD services, and the need to respond to the growing Americanization of cultural consumption within the EU.

The EU Audiovisual Media Services Directive (2018) represents a critical step in introducing quotas on the catalogues of the VoD services providers, reflecting EU's long-lasting policy to create a common audiovisual market (Farchy et al., 2022). The minimum content quotas appeared in the European audiovisual field as a mechanism for ensuring the public dissemination of the European works against a background of American audiovisual predominance. Even today, the platformization has dramatically changed peoples' watching habits and the economic model in the audiovisual industry (Evens & Donders, 2018). This type of protectionist measure aims at enhancing intra-European productions and bringing online users in contact with more European content. Nevertheless, it has been argued that EU quotas have proved to bear little dynamic in strengthening the circulation of European audiovisual productions among the European countries (Micova, 2013).

The Article 13 of the amended AVMSD stipulates that financial contribu-

tions to the production of European works may be imposed on the providers of VoD services, however EU member states are entitled to decide on whether and to what extent these financial contributions can be implemented. Moreover, thanks to the latest AVMSD, the concept of prominence was expanded to incorporate the promotion of European content in the online video services. The Directive, however, does not define specific prominence measures but leaves the implementation of the obligation open to several possibilities.

In general, the major requirements and the setting of their implementation, defined by the European Directive, might be summarized as follows:

- A minimum of 30 percent quotas regarding the European works is defined as a compulsory obligation, accompanied by the need for these productions to be brought to public attention.
- This obligation does not concern providers characterized by a limited audience or low revenues and is to be fulfilled either based on locally produced works or on influential productions coming from other EU members or European countries being involved in the European Convention on Transfrontier Television.
- Financial contributions intended for European productions are non-obligatory both in the case of linear and non-linear services.
- Multiple types of contributions are permissible such as direct contributions to the audiovisual productions, acquisition of rights or taxes payable to formulate a fund bound for the audiovisual sector.

The new Article 13 allows states not only to impose financial contributions on media service providers but also demand contributions from providers targeting their audience, even in cases when they are based in another member - state. The essence of financial contributions is argued to lie in that - compared to the measure of minimum quotas - they reflect “a more straightforward while flexible mechanism”, playing a considerable role in promoting audiovisual diversity in terms of consumption and production, setting aside any discrimination against foreign works (García Leiva et al., 2021).

On the other hand, the imposition for inclusion of European works within catalogues of the VoD providers is argued to reflect a protectionist measure that does not entail their consumption nor their visibility (*ibid*). The compulsory obligations of minimum 30 percent share and prominence for European works, as set by the new Directive, are supposed to present challenges related to the lack of a common methodology in defining the share of European works and to the absence of a well-defined approach to achieve prominence. These challenges endanger consistency among EU members as to the implementation of the new

normative provisions (ibid) In effect, comparing the transposition of Article 13 of the AVMSD into the national legislation of the EU member states, what is revealed is a high degree of heterogeneity (Komorowski et al., 2021).

RESEARCH METHOD AND QUESTIONS

Gaining access to information regarding the consumption of VoD platforms can present considerable difficulties. However, there are only a handful of websites that offer some information in this regard. One prominent and already tested example is the FlixPatrol {<https://flixpatrol.com/>} platform. It aggregates consumption data from 2020 and onward for six major platforms in 156 countries. These platforms are Netflix, Amazon Prime, HBO Max, Disney+, iTunes, and Google TV. FlixPatrol provides data on consumption patterns categorized by region, genre, and production company and can be used to access data based on the four geographic regions (UCAN, EMEA, LATAM, APAC) or even to overview specific countries. However, the availability of consumption data varies greatly among different platforms with Netflix being the most transparent.

Data on Netflix catalogues can be accessed on FlixPatrol {<https://flixwatch.co/>}, the so - called “unofficial Netflix Search Engine”, where one can find data for Netflix libraries in over 30 countries. Worldwide data is also available concerning the number of Netflix titles, genres, original audio and IMDB ratings, among others. This data should be treated with caution, however, since due to limited duration of licence agreements, the number of titles in each country varies constantly. Another important limitation is that both platforms report on number of titles in national catalogues without differentiating between films and series. Therefore, we were forced to treat both kinds of content as a single entity.

Based on the theoretical framework, analysed above, the major questions raised by this study can be summarized as follows:

- How much national or European is the programming flow of SVoD platforms?
- Does US content uniformly dominate across SVoD catalogues, providing still validity to arguments regarding one-way flow in the audiovisual field?
- Are there common consumption patterns on SVoD platforms across EU countries in terms of genres’ preferences indicating a trend of homogeneity?
- Are there indications of human curated recommendations and algorithms’ influence on the consumption patterns found on SVoD platforms?

NATIONAL CATALOGUES AND CONTENT AVAILABILITY

As we have already highlighted, North American content consumption is predominant throughout all VoD platforms. However, the consumption of European content varies significantly through time and between platforms. The main factor that drives content consumption on these platforms is the availability of content. Despite EU regulation, geo-blocking is still applied for the countries of the EU, pushing further the fragmentation of the European market. However, when examining the European catalogues in comparison to non – EU countries some common characteristics can be observed.

Taking under examination the catalogues of Netflix, where European content is the most prominent in terms of consumption, there are several notable particularities. First and foremost, data collected for 2021 show that Ireland, the Baltic countries and Eastern European countries have more titles in their libraries compared to other EU regions (chart 1). This trend could be attributed to a combination of factors such as national costs per title and regional licensing agreements, as well as factors that have to do with the platforms' competitive positioning and wider market strategy (revenue, number of subscribers, competitors etc.) (Moody, 2024).

European catalogues include older movies compared to catalogues in other parts of the world. According to the available data (chart 2), the European catalogue, along with the Japanese and the Icelandic one, includes more titles from the 1920s to 1979 in comparison to the rest of the world. On the contrary, Asian catalogues include more titles from the 1980s and the 1990s (see appendix).

Moreover, countries of Central and Eastern Europe include more quality titles in terms of IMDB ratings compared to the rest of Europe. Specifically for 2021, according to the available data (as displayed in chart 1) Ireland has the catalogue with the most quality movies in Europe (778 titles), followed by Serbia (751), Bulgaria (742), Hungary (741), Romania (747), Slovenia (745), Slovakia (738), the Czech Republic (736), Croatia (740), the Ukraine (727), Russia (725), Lithuania (721) and Latvia (710). The same countries seem to have richer libraries regarding their medium quality titles according to IMDB ratings (from 6 to 7.9), as shown in chart 4 (see appendix). In terms of content genres, these countries incorporate more drama, comedy, crime, and documentary titles in their Netflix libraries (see appendix).

Chart 1: Number of titles in Netflix national catalogues in 2021:

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixwatch.co, 2021

Chart 2: National catalogues on Netflix including titles from 1920 – 1979:

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixwatch.co, 2021

BREAKDOWN OF GLOBAL CONSUMPTION BY GEOGRAPHICAL AREA

When analyzing global content consumption of the six most popular VoD platforms in the period from 2020 to 2022, we detect some common patterns. As seen in graph 1, the consumption of North - American content is predominant (from 55% in 2020 to 64% in 2021) throughout the period for the Netflix case. On the other hand, the consumption of European content was 37.4% during the first quarter of 2020, then dropped to its lowest point during the third quarter of 2021 (16.9%), only to rise again up to 24.5% during the last quarter of 2022.

In the case of Netflix, it can be argued that the consumption of American content is not correlated to the consumption of the European one. On the contrary, the research findings reveal that when the consumption of European content drops, the consumption of Asian content and, to a lesser degree, of Latin American content replaces it. Therefore, when it comes to global consumption on Netflix, it is observed that the predominance of North – American content cannot be challenged by the smaller regional markets. It seems that the smaller markets of Europe, Asia and Latin America compete for the second place in the global content consumption.

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com

The situation is different regarding content consumption on HBO. On this platform the consumption of north – American content and European content demonstrates a complementary relationship.

In graph 2 it is clearly visible that when the consumption of North-American content drops (from Q2 2020 to Q4 2020) the consumption of European content increases equally. Similarly, when the consumption of North – American content increases (from Q1 2021 to Q2 2021) the consumption of European content equally decreases.

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com

As it pertains to the Netflix case, the consumption of north – American content on Amazon prime is challenged by the two smaller markets of Asia and Europe. However, the consumption of Asian content outperforms the European one from 2020 to 2021 and it is only for a short period of time (from Q4 2021 to Q1 2022) that the European content performs better than the Asian one (graph 3).

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com

On Disney+, the dominance of North – American content is total throughout the period. A small drop in the consumption during the third quarter of 2021 is accompanied by a small increase of consumption of Latin American content. Content coming from other regions of the world is almost non – existent on this platform (graph 1 in appendix).

Content consumption on iTunes resembles the HBO case. In this case again, the North – American content and the European one display a complementary relationship. The relevant data (graph 2 in appendix) clearly reveal that when North – American content increases during the second quarter of 2020, while the first quarter of 2022 the consumption of the European one decreases equally.

Consumption patterns on Google TV follow the trend of iTunes and HBO. The dominance of North – American content is only meekly challenged by the European one. When the consumption of European content increases the consumption of North – American content decreases and the opposite. The small rise of Asian content consumption from the Q2 2020 to Q2 2021 is insufficient to compete with the other two markets (graph 3 in appendix).

CONSUMPTION ON NETFLIX FOR TEN EUROPEAN COUNTRIES BY COUNTRY OF ORIGIN

The analysis on consumption patterns in ten European countries highlights that US content overwhelmingly dominates, with content derived from the UK following with a big distance in terms of popularity (graph 4). However, it is also noteworthy that in several countries including Turkey, Italy, Spain, the Czech Republic, and Germany, the consumption of local content holds a significant position. On the other hand, content originating from other EU countries, including France with its well-established audiovisual industry, as well as content from other parts of the world, exhibit comparatively lower levels of consumption on Netflix.

Graph 4: Consumption on Netflix for 10 European countries by country of origin

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com

CONTENT PREFERENCES BY GENRE – THE NETFLIX CASE

As demonstrated above, different countries include various titles in their libraries that can be categorized according to their year of release, their quality based on IMDB ratings and their genres. In this section, we examine the consumption of various genres from 2020 to 2022. For our examination we included six out of the most popular genres as recorded on flixpatrol.com in the Q1 of 2022, namely drama (24%), comedy (14.1%) and action (8.7%).

As shown in the graphs below (from graph 5 to 7) the consumption for all genres in all countries follow the same trends throughout different periods of time. One explanation for the recorded patterns is that audiences' consumption is mainly driven by the promotion of certain titles implemented by the recommendation algorithms on Netflix platform and much less on users' individual search..

Graph 5: Genre preferences on Netflix by country: Drama

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com

Graph 6: Genre preferences on Netflix by country: Comedy

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com

Graph 7: Genre preferences on Netflix by country: Action

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com

CONTENT PREFERENCES BY GENRE ON HBO

Whereas Netflix is relying on its algorithm recommendations and advanced machine learning for keeping viewers engaged while browsing its huge catalogues, the newly launched HBO Max platform is focusing more and more on human curated recommendations, while still using algorithms. By using human curated recommendations, which are more sophisticated, HBO aims at users' greater engagement and longer retention. Another benefit of this tactic is that HBO platform is not as vulnerable to feedback loops and filter bubbles that may end up pushing their users away.

For the aforementioned reasons, we decided to look more into the HBO case regarding genres consumption and compare the results with Netflix. For the analysis we considered again the most popular genres as recorded by Flixpatrol for the Q1 of 2022. The most popular genres for this period were drama (22%), comedy (18%), and sci-fi (11.9%). The data displayed in the graphs 8, 9 and 10 reveal that consumption in Bulgaria and in the Czech Republic follows in most of the cases the same patterns, while consumption in Portugal is mostly aligned to that of Sweden and to a lesser degree to Spain. One more interesting finding is that since Q2 of 2022 the consumption pattern is almost identical in all countries under investigation.

Graph 8: Genre preferences on HBO by country: Drama

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com

Graph 9: Genre preferences on HBO by country: Comedy

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com

Graph 10: Genre preferences on HBO by country: Sci-fi

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The present research reveals that with a few exceptions, there seems to exist common patterns of content preferences across all the investigated countries. This finding confirms that the so-called trend of the transnational aspect of television programming (Esser, 2007) and television consumption are still existent (Esser, 2002). Current audiovisual content is distributed transnationally through the global streaming providers, instead of the international television networks of the past, which had contributed to the transnationalization and approximation of European television programming (Esser, 2007). These trends are now applicable by the global online platforms based on a different operational rationale promoting platformization as the dominant structure in the audiovisual economy. After all, many studies have already concluded that a globalizing trend pushed by VoD platforms has been occurring, one that is taking the focus off of cultural specificities and instead placing it on creating content focused on locations and long-established audience associations (Hansen, 2022).

In this contemporary global industry of cultural aesthetics, US-based SVoD platforms have succeeded in giving the pace in the global audiovisual politics and economy. National European media operators are trying to adapt their strategies in a new and even more competitive framework of conditions regarding the production, distribution, and consumption of this audiovisual

content. The multifaceted strategy of US SVoD platforms, as exemplified by Netflix, consists of financial deals with regional and national pay-TV operators, funds provisions to cultural institutions, investments in original content, partnerships with film sales and distribution companies. By co-producing and investing in local content, streamers are demonstrating in practice that strict regulation for SVoD platforms endangers the efficiency of a business model that serves the needs of the market, as well as audiences' need for greater content diversity (Vlasis, 2021a). It seems that platforms reached the quotas requirement by flooding the EU libraries with mostly old European productions, whose copyrights could be acquired at a lesser cost compared to newer productions. While one might consider acquiring old productions as a sign of European audiences' preference for more classic audiovisual works, no one can really attest to the quality of the selected works.

Further, the study has brought to the fore two important findings regarding Netflix libraries. First, quotas do not seem to influence the consumption of audiovisual works in countries with strong audiovisual industries. To the contrary, these countries reveal a strong preference for their own national productions, almost ignoring other European works. Extrapolating from this fact, it is easy to understand the "cultural exemption" policies come accompanied by a strong bias in favor of countries with strong audiovisual industries. Secondly, surprisingly Netflix libraries do not seem to follow market logic. While one would expect that richer libraries would be found in countries with higher GDP per capita, where a higher subscription could be commanded, in praxis the direct opposite happens. Among EU27 the most extensive libraries are found in the Balkan region with the sole exception of Ireland, while the least are found in the Nordic countries.

Additionally, research findings explicitly indicate the predominance of US content in the consumption patterns emerged in all SVoD platforms of the sample over the period 2020-2022. On several platforms, the presence of European works in the audience's preferences as well as the explicit fluctuations displayed by the European content overall, often in a complementary relationship with the dominant American content (in such a way that the decline of the one affects the rise of the other and vice versa) reveals that the dominant role of the United States in global audiovisual flows remains unchallenged by the European audiovisual ventures. The balance of power in the digital non-linear audiovisual landscape seems to follow the line that has long been established in the global film market; the asymmetry in favor of the United States has led the European film market being "an integrated feature of the US economy" in the context of Hollywood's domination (Vlasis, 2021b). However, the findings don't necessarily constitute a condemna-

tion of the quotas policy. To the contrary, if this complementary relationship between US and European content holds under extensive testing, it would mean that increased quotas could bring a better balance between European and American works. Of course, further studies must be conducted in all platforms to better understand this complementary relationship.

Moreover, EU policy results after a multiple variable evaluation have been described as governed by “a logic à la carte” (Vlassis, 2021b). At the same time, the supremacy of US VoD services, in terms of audiovisual content flows, is fueled by several stable advantages characterizing US-based online platforms. These are the large pool of domestic content consumers, the popularity of the English language, the capacity to produce works in multiple languages, as well as their inclination for synergetic strategies (Vlassis, 2021b: 595) It appears that transnational SVoD providers, such as Netflix, by adopting an expansion strategy of their international presence, have led to a redefinition of successful-popular television flows based on global terms. In this regard, it has been argued that the discourses of streaming success, articulated by Netflix executives and creative personnel, point to the formulation of Netflix’s audience as global and undifferentiated (Wayne et al., 2023).

Regarding policy, an important caveat to keep in mind is that the EU does not currently demand VoD platforms to publish data in a uniform way. That means that, unfortunately, while policy makers could have access to some data, this is not comparable. As a result, any policy taken on the issue of VoD platforms is condemned to remain partial and ultimately ineffective. To surpass this problem, the EU should proceed with publishing uniform guidelines for all VoD platforms.

As Lotz, Eklund and Soroka argue: “even though global streamers have reconfigured storytelling norms in some ways, they also expand the tyranny of the pursuit of economies of scale that drives media industries and leads to inequitable circulation and commissioning” (Lotz et al., 2022). Under these circumstances, the protection of European cultures is a highly challenging task which may presuppose the increase of the 30% quota obligation requested by providers of on-demand audiovisual services. The policy inefficiency related to the 30% content quota reveals the highly contested character of the audiovisual policy which needs to cater for balancing priorities among media systems with different socio-political features.

New mechanisms applied to SVoD services might as well be derived from national governments in Europe which are entitled to request from non-national SVoD platforms to make investments in national and European audiovisual works based on a rate dictated by their net turnover achieved in the respective European country. This measure has been already announced

in several EU countries, including France, where the government is asking non-national SVoD services providers to invest 20% of their turnover in French and European audiovisual productions (Keslassy, 2021).

Back in the 1980s, the concern was over the “défi américain” (the American challenge), but in the first decade of the 21st century, according to Jeremy Tunstall (2008) “the European and American media are becoming a single Euro-American media industry”. The question being raised is whether the same applies in the platformized era or whether OTT platforms make the audiovisual consumption less inclined to the US production. Chalaby (2022), by pointing to the more cosmopolitan character of SVoD’s catalogues compared to broadcasting programs, foresees that the global streamers have the potential to give birth to a *new transcultural order*, accomplished through the availability of a TV culture that is deprived of national borders and restrictions.

In an evolving audiovisual context in which US production still holds a “commanding position” and American media formats (i.e., TV series, documentaries, etc.) are widely copied around the world, it is reasonable to ask whether the OTT platforms, such as Netflix and Amazon Prime, can strike a new balance. A potential reply is very unlikely if one sees the attraction of US programming in OTT platforms. Perhaps, thinking that surfing is just another national game, it can be argued, following Tunstall’s viewpoint, that people prefer to be informed and entertained by people “who look the same, talk the same, joke the same, behave the same” as they do (2007: xiv). But the question remains, whether this homogenization, that has been so successful for the US, can be implemented in a European context.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT AND DISCLAIMER

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101004488. The information and views in this publication are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions or bodies, nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained herein.

REFERENCES

- Aguiar, L., & Waldfogel, J. (2018). Netflix: global hegemon or facilitator of frictionless digital trade?. *Journal of Cultural Economics*, 42, 419-445.
- AVMSD. (2018, November 28). Directive (EU) 2018/1808 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 14 November 2018 amending Directive 2010/13/EU on the coordination of certain provisions laid down by law, regulation or administrative action in Member States concerning the provision of audiovisual media services (Audiovisual Media Services Directive) in view of changing market realities, *Official Journal of the European Union*. Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2018/1808/oj>
- Chalaby, J. K. (2023). The streaming industry and the platform economy: An analysis. *Media, Culture & Society*, 46(3), 552-571. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01634437231210439>
- Chalaby, J. K. (2022). Global streamers: Placing the transnational at the heart of TV culture. *Journal of Digital Media & Policy*, 13(2), 223-241.
- Chalaby, J. (2016). Television and Globalization: The TV Content Global Value Chain. *Journal of Communication*, 66(1), 35-59. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcom.12203>
- Chalaby, J. K. (2015). The advent of the transnational TV format trading system: a global commodity chain analysis. *Media, Culture & Society*, 37(3), 460-478. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0163443714567017>
- Esser, A. (2007). Audiovisual content in Europe: Transnationalization and approximation. *Journal of Contemporary European Studies*, 15(2), 163-184.
- Esser, A. (2002). The transnationalization of European television. *Journal of European Area Studies*, 10(1), 13-29.
- Evens, T., & Donders, K. (2018). *Platform power and policy in transforming television markets*. Palgrave Macmillan.
- European Commission. (2023, May 17). *The European Media Industry Outlook (Commission Staff Working Document)*. Brussels, SWD (2023) 150 final. Retrieved from: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/european-media-industry-outlook>
- Farchy, J., Bideau, G., & Tallec, S. (2022). Content quotas and prominence on VoD services: New challenges for European audiovisual regulators. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 28(4), 419-430.
- García Leiva, T., Alborno, L., & Gómez García, R. (2021). Netflix and the transnationalization of the audiovisual industry in the Ibero-American space. *Comunicación y Sociedad*, 1-18. <https://doi.org/10.32870/cys.v2021.8238>
- García Leiva, M. T., & Alborno, L. A. (2021). VOD service providers and regulation in the European Union: an audiovisual diversity approach. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 27(3), 267-281.

- Grece, C. (2022). *Film and TV content in TVoD, SVoD and FOD catalogues - 2022 Edition*. European Audiovisual Observatory & Council of Europe. Retrieved from <https://rm.coe.int/VoD-catalogues-2022-film-and-tv-content-2022-edition-c-grece/1680a9b5d7>
- Hansen, K. T. (2020). From Nordic Noir to Euro Noir: Nordic Noir Influencing European Serial SVoD Drama. *Nordic Noir, Adaptation, Appropriation*, 275-294.
- Iordache, C., Raats, T., & Afilipoaie, A. (2022). Transnationalisation revisited through the Netflix Original: An analysis of investment strategies in Europe. *Convergence*, 28(1), 236-254.
- Jin, D. Y. (2013). The construction of platform imperialism in the globalization era. *TripleC: Communication, Capitalism & Critique. Open Access Journal for a Global Sustainable Information Society*, 11(1), 145-172.
- Keslassy, E. (2021, June 30). Netflix, Amazon must invest 20-25% of French revenues in local content, France government decrees, *Variety Magazine*. Retrieved from <https://variety.com/2021/streaming/global/avms-france-netflix-new-rules-streamers-1235008364/> (accessed 5/6/2023).
- Komorowski, M., Iordache, C., Kostovska, I., Tintel, S., & Raats, T. (2021). Investment obligations for VOD providers to financially contribute to the production of European works, a 2021 update. *Studies on Media, Information and Telecommunication (SMIT)*, 2.
- Lobato, R. (2018). Rethinking international TV flows research in the age of Netflix. *Television & New Media*, 19(3), 241-256.
- Lobato, R., & Scarlata, A. (2022). Regulating discoverability in subscription video-on-demand services. In *Digital Platform Regulation: Global Perspectives on Internet Governance* (pp. 209-227). Springer International Publishing.
- Lobato, R., & Lotz, A. (2021). Beyond streaming wars: Rethinking competition in video services. *Media Industries*, 8(1), 89-108.
- Lotz, D. A. (2019). The multifaceted policy challenges of transnational Internet-distributed television. *Journal of Digital Media & Policy*, 10(1): 27-31. https://doi.org/10.1386/jdmp.10.1.27_1
- Lotz, D. A. (2017). *Portals: A treatise on internet-distributed television*. Michigan Publishing.
- Lotz, A. D., Eklund, O., & Soroka, S. (2022). Netflix, library analysis, and globalization: Rethinking mass media flows. *Journal of Communication*, 72(4), 511-521.
- Micova, S. B. (2013). Content quotas: What and whom are they protecting?. In *Private television in Western Europe: Content, markets, policies* (pp. 245-259). Palgrave Macmillan UK.

- Moody, R. (2020). Netflix subscribers and revenue by country. *Comparitech*. Retrieved from: [Netflix Subscribers and Revenue by Country \[2024 version\] \(comparitech.com\)](https://www.comparitech.com/netflix-subscribers-and-revenue-by-country-2024/)
- Pardo, A. (2012). Digital Hollywood: How Internet and Social media are changing the movie business. In *Handbook of social media management: Value chain and business models in changing media markets* (pp. 327-347). Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Schneeberger, A. (2023) *Audiovisual media services in Europe - 2022 edition*. Retrieved from: <https://rm.coe.int/audiovisual-media-services-in-europe-2022-edition-a-schneeberger/1680a99e7d>
- Straubhaar, J., Santillana, M., de Macedo Higgins Joyce, V., Duarte, L. G., Straubhaar, J., Santillana, M., ... & Duarte, L. G. (2021). Streaming Television, Netflix, and Transverse Transnationalism. In *From Telenovelas to Netflix: Transnational, Transverse Television in Latin America* (pp. 159-201).
- Tunstall, J. (2008). *The media were American: US mass media in decline. (No Title)*.
- Vlassis, A. (2021a). Global online platforms, COVID-19, and culture: The global pandemic, an accelerator towards which direction?. *Media, Culture & Society*, 43(5), 957-969.
- Vlassis, A. (2021b). European Union and online platforms in global audiovisual politics and economy: Once Upon a Time in America?. *International Communication Gazette*, 83(6), 593-615.
- Wayne, M. L., & Uribe Sandoval, A. C. (2023). Netflix original series, global audiences and discourses of streaming success. *Critical Studies in Television*, 18(1), 81-100.

Appendix

Chart 1: National Catalogues on Netflix including titles from 1980 – 1989

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixwatch.co, 2021

Chart 2: National Catalogues on Netflix including titles from 1990 – 1999

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixwatch.co, 2021

Chart 3: National Catalogues on Netflix including titles with high IMDB ratings (above 8)

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixwatch.co, 2021

Chart 4: National Catalogues on Netflix including titles with medium IMDB ratings (6.0 – 7.9)

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixwatch.co, 2021

GRAPHS

Graph 1: Content preferences by region of origin on Disney+

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com

Graph 2: Content preferences by region of origin on iTunes

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com

Graph 3: Content preferences by region on Google TV

Source: Eumeplat Project, data compilation and elaboration based on flixpatrol.com